

Application, results and perceptions of a think-aloud study in listening comprehension of Spanish

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The present article outlines the procedure and shows the outcomes of a think-aloud study intended to, first, find out what listening strategies Hong Kong students of Spanish use to comprehend a particular oral passage in the target language, second, discover what strategies the learners perceive to be the most effective, and, third, understand the participants' perceptions of the think-aloud protocol. Such a protocol was developed during interviews in which students listened to a text in Spanish, and were asked to verbalize the processes they were using. After listening, they completed five comprehension questions, reflected on their strategic behaviour, and evaluated the protocol itself. Results reveal that problem identification and evaluation are the most used strategies; while the strategies of focusing attention, note taking, and cooperation are reported to be the most effective ones. Findings also show that students have a very positive view of the developed think-aloud protocol.

Keywords: learning strategies; listening comprehension; verbal report; think-aloud; Spanish as a foreign language

1. Introduction

Listening involves mental processes which are not easily observable, nor are strategies used to accomplish this activity. Think-aloud has been the preferred method of eliciting from learners their strategy use when listening (Macaro, Graham, and Vanderplank, 2007). Think-aloud refers to the stream-of consciousness disclosure of thought processes while listening to information (Ericsson and Simon, 1993). The procedure of the think-aloud protocol requires subjects to listen to an audio (Murphy, 1985) or to watch a video excerpt (Long, 1991) which is paused at pre-set points, usually corresponding to idea units or transitions in the text (Peters, 1999; Vandergrift, 1997). At each pause point, the subjects are asked to state, in the shared language they agree, what listening strategies they are using (Rost, 2011).

According to Afflerbach (2000), much of the research in second or foreign language contexts using think-aloud reports has provided little information about key aspects of this methodology. Even though it has been more than a decade since this assertion was made, and several studies in the field of listening (such as Santos, Graham, and Vanderplank, 2008) have published useful descriptions of their methodologies ever since, the present study attempts to fulfill this weakness, and thus contribute to deepen our understanding of some key methodological issues of think-aloud protocols intended to research into second language listening strategies.

In addition to the methodological contribution, the present study attempts to find out the listening strategies the participants use to comprehend an oral passage in Spanish, as well as the strategies they report to be the most effective. Furthermore, participants were divided into three groups depending on the scores they obtained in the given comprehension questions with the objective of investigating the listening strategies used

by the most-, middle-, and less-effective listeners. The study is also intended to learn more about the students' perceptions of the think-aloud protocol as a way of assessing the implemented protocol.

2. Relevant literature

Previous research into listening strategy use employing a think-aloud protocol has taken different approaches. Some studies have studied strategy use at one time point; other studies have focused on listening strategy development; while other ones have explored the effects of strategy instruction on L2 listening strategy use.

The first studies which employed a think-aloud procedure for L2 listening research focused on strategy use at one time point. This is the case of Murphy (1985), who explored the listening strategies of 12 ESL college students divided into more proficient and less proficient listeners. He was able to label six broad strategic categories (recalling, speculating, probing, introspecting, delaying, and recording) that encompassed a total of 17 separate strategies. He found evidence of the differences between the two groups of ESL listeners in relation to the frequencies of the strategies they used, and to the sequential patterns they followed.

Chamot and Küpper (1989) investigated the differences in listening strategies between effective and less effective high school learners using a think-aloud procedure in which students were interviewed individually. Results suggest that, in the listening tasks, the highly effective listeners used the strategies of elaboration (by using the given comprehension questions to get a mind set on what they were going to hear and to recall what they already knew about the topic), inferencing (by predicting possible content), selective attention (by focusing on important content), and self-monitoring (by correcting or confirming their predictions).

Bacon (1992) conducted an experiment in which learners listened to two radio broadcasts in Spanish, and reported on their strategies, comprehension, learning, level of confidence, and affective response to this input. She found that more successful listeners, first, moved from bottom-up to top-down strategies as they progressed from the perceptual to the parsing phases of comprehension, and, second, made useful connections with the background knowledge during the utilization phase.

Vandergrift (1997) used a think-aloud procedure in which high school students of French reported on their thought processes with the objective of studying the relationship between the types of listening strategies reported, the frequency of their use, and the differences in reported use across four variables (level of language proficiency, gender, listening ability, and learning style). He classified students as more and less successful listeners depending on the frequency, variety, and sophistication of strategy use. Vandergrift (1997) found clear differences in reported strategy use by listening ability and proficiency level. He concluded that the use of metacognitive strategies, such as comprehension monitoring, problem identification, and selective attention, appeared to be the significant factor distinguishing the successful from the less successful listeners. However, differences for gender were minimal, and differences for learning style were inconclusive.

Some years later, Vandergrift (2003) used the same think-aloud procedure with the purpose of examining the types of strategies used and the differences in strategy use by more skilled and less skilled listeners (in total 36 grade 7 students of French) while these students listened to authentic texts in the target language. The author found out that more skilled listeners significantly employed less translation, more metacognitive strategies, more questioning elaboration, and more monitoring than the less skilled listeners.

Other studies (such as Graham, Santos, and Vanderplank, 2008; Graham, Santos, and Vanderplank, 2011) investigated the development of strategy use over time in the absence of explicit strategy training. Graham et al. (2008) examined how the relationship between learners' listening proficiency and strategic behaviour developed over 6 months in two lower-intermediate learners of L2 French (one was a high scorer, while the other one, a low scorer) when there was no explicit strategy training. They gathered data on the learners' strategic behaviour from verbal reports made by learners while they were completing a multiple-choice listening task. Results show a high degree of stability of strategy use over the time period, with pre-existing differences between the high and low scorer persisting.

Graham et al. (2011) employed recall protocols and verbal reports in order to investigate the development of the strategy use (and also of the listening proficiency) of 15 lower-intermediate learners of French in England. They considered whether listeners remained in the same listening proficiency group (distinguishing between non-movers, improvers and decliners) after six months, and whether changes in strategy use were related to movement or non-movement between listening proficiency groups. Data from recall protocols were gathered at two time points (Time 1 and Time 2) in which students listened to the recording and were asked to write everything they had understood. In an effort to try to capture students' usual way of listening, learners were also asked to make verbal reports while they completed a multiple choice listening task. Graham et al. (2011) concluded that beneath changes in frequency of strategy use lies a degree of stability in manner of use, especially for non-movers and decliners. They also found that differences in strategy use between groups, that were present at Time 1 and continued at Time 2, were more evident than changes in strategy use between the two time points. Therefore,

differences in strategy use were more evident between groups (non-movers, improvers and decliners) than between uses from Time 1 to Time 2.

Another approach to research investigating listening strategy use focuses on exploring the impact of strategy instruction on L2 listener strategy use. In this line, Yeldham and Gruba (2016) employed task-based verbal reports to gain insight into the learners' listening strategies, pre- and post-instruction. The results showed how all learners developed a greater balance in their use of top-down and bottom-up strategies, mainly by selectively integrating suitable strategies from the course into their listening repertoires.

Despite the fact that verbal reports give a fuller picture of strategy use than other methods such as questionnaires can do (Graham et al., 2011), there have been some concerns about its validity and use. The think-aloud measure has been criticized for being too time-consuming (Boring, 1953), having a potential intrusive effect (Mann, 1982), and revealing incomplete or irrelevant cognitive processes (Ericsson and Simon, 1984, 1993). The main controversy, empirically addressed for the first time by Leow and Morgan-Short (2004), and deeply studied by Bowles and Leow (2005), Sachs and Suh (2007), and Bowles (2008, 2010), is that think-aloud might be reactive, that is "... that requiring participants to think aloud while they perform a task may affect the task performance and therefore not be a true reflection of normal cognitive processing" (Bowles, 2010, 3). Considering the mixed findings of such prior studies, we understand that the extent of reactivity depends on different factors related to the protocol's method such as type of verbal report, language of verbal report, language of task, type of task, and proficiency in the target language, among other. In this regard, we strongly believe that reactivity can be minimized and even avoided by paying careful attention to research procedures; that

is why, the present article provides detailed information of the think-aloud protocol and its methodology.

3. Methods and instruments

3.1. Objectives and structure

The present article reports on a think-aloud study and provides a detailed explanation of the key methodological aspects related to the developed think-aloud protocol. The reported study intends to, first, discover what listening strategies Hong Kong students employ to comprehend a specific oral passage in Spanish, second, determine what strategies the learners (divided into three groups depending on the obtained scores in the listening comprehension task) report to be the most useful, and, third, understand the students' perceptions of the think-aloud protocol.

The first objective aims to seek introspective data reflecting students' report of the mental processes they undergo while listening to a text in Spanish, and, therefore, it does not imply intervention, but reportage of thought processes.

The resulting introspective data are meant to be transcribed, analysed, categorized, and quantified in order to shed light on the listening strategies used by the participants during the protocol.

The second objective focuses on retrospective data collected through an open-ended question in which students individually assess the effectiveness of the strategies they used, and consider which strategies were the most effective.

The data collection procedure used to address the third objective is a closed-ended evaluation questionnaire in which the respondents are required to indicate different degrees of agreement towards five given statements related to the think-aloud protocol.

Therefore, the resulting data is quantitative in nature.

The present study embraces two think-aloud protocols, a pilot and a final one, which were applied during two different sets of interviews. The pilot think-aloud protocol was conducted during the first set of interviews with the objective of testing the think-aloud protocol, identify aspects that could be improved, and make the proper adjustments in order to improve the protocol. The implementation of the pilot think-aloud protocol was analysed and evaluated by the teacher. Three main weaknesses were identified, namely the insufficient rigidity of the protocol, the lack of training in how to think aloud, and the selective transcription of information regarding listening strategies. These three weaknesses were modified, adjusted and fine-tuned for the final think-aloud procedure in order to get an improved technique.

3.2. *Participants*

Eight participants took part in the exploratory or pilot protocol, and 19 learners participated in the final one. All the participants were students who registered in the sub-groups of two intact classes in two different semesters, SPAN2001 and SPAN2002, taught by the teacher-researcher (referred as female from now on), and who agreed to participate by signing a consent form. Such a consent form, on the one hand, invited students to participate in the research study, and, on the other, specified the title and the purpose of the study, the procedures, the potential benefits, the confidentiality and the researcher's contact information. As this research involved human participants, we applied and obtained ethical approval by the Human Research Ethics Committee for Non-Clinical Faculties (HRECNCf).

The participants were Hong Kong students of Spanish who were in their second year at The University of Hong Kong. All the participants spoke Cantonese as their mother tongue, English as their L2 and Mandarin as their L3. They were between 18 and

21 years old. They all successfully passed the previous course in Spanish language (SPAN1002) which was equivalent to an A2 according to the guidelines set out by the *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages* (Council of Europe, 2001). Thus, the participants had reached an A2 level of proficiency in Spanish and were initiating the level B1 using the textbook *Gente 2* (Martín Peris and Sans Baulenas, 2004).

Once the final protocol was conducted and the answers to the comprehension questions were analysed, participants in the final protocol were grouped into three even groups according to the scores they obtained in the comprehension questions (See Table 1). We opted to classify students into groups after and not before the experiment (as O'Malley, Chamot, and Küpper 1989, did), because we agree with White (2008) that this prior classification might have prejudiced the findings. Participants in the first group were the most effective listeners since they understood more than 70% of the whole passage, and thus achieved a grade A (also A- and A+) or B (also B- and B+). Students in group 2 understood between 50-69.9% of the oral text, and, therefore, scored C (also C- and C+) in the listening task. Finally, learners in group 3 obtained a grade D or F, since they understood less than 50% of the oral passage. All participants were assigned numbers in order to be referred to anonymously.

Group	Students	Scores in the listening comprehension task
1	2	100
	13	100
	19	87.5
	8	71.9
	12	71.9
	15	71.9
2	3	65.6
	10	65.6

2	1	62.5
	7	59.4
	9	59.4
	11	53.1
	14	50
3	16	34.4
	18	34.4
	17	31.3
	6	28.1
	5	25
	4	12.5

3.3. Think-aloud protocol

The final think-aloud protocol was structured in four phases: planning, preparation, development and analysis.

Planning phase

In the planning phase, the researcher considered the needs and interests of the participants, thought of possible dates to conduct the interviews, drafted the steps of the protocol, arranged preparation materials, selected the oral input to be listened, and developed some tasks to gauge students' comprehension, several self-assessment activities, and the evaluation questionnaire.

Preparation phase

In the preparation phase, once in class, the teacher informed the students about the protocol and provided them with the preparation materials that should be read at home prior to the interview's date. Those materials consisted of: (a) a paragraph detailing place, date, time, duration, objective and procedure of the interviews; (b) a reference to the chapter of the book *How to be a more successful language learner* by Rubin and Thompson (1994) devoted to listening, and (c) a list of listening strategies which included

the name and the type of strategy (adapted from Vandergrift and Gogh, 2012), a brief description, a list of enabling tactics, and a related picture for every strategy. After submitting all these documents, the teacher made sure that the students understood the purpose and procedure of the interviews, and made appointments with them according to their availability (students picked a classmate to attend the interview with).

Development phase

The development phase involved the actual think-aloud protocol. The students attended interviews in pairs, with one classmate of their choice. Interviews were conducted in the researcher's office and, as a consequence, classroom context was inevitably changed for methodological purposes. Due to ethical issues, these interviews were audio (and not video) recorded. Interviews were structured into thirteen steps:

- (1) Welcome: The teacher welcomed and thanked the students for attending the interview.
 - (2) Warm-up: The teacher submitted the worksheet. This document included: (a) a summary of the listening strategies sorted by type; (b) a reminder of the objective and procedure of the protocol; (c) instructions for every listening (first, second, third, and fourth); (d) five comprehension tasks; (e) the transcription of the oral text; (f) several self-assessment questions, and (g) the evaluation questionnaire.
- In order to turn the conversation towards Spanish and towards listening, the teacher also asked the students whether they usually had trouble understanding spoken Spanish and, in such cases, what difficulties they normally faced and what strategies they typically used to improve their comprehension.

- (3) Objective and procedure specification: The teacher explained both the objective, and the procedure of the protocol. We decided to use both interrupted (for the first listening) and uninterrupted (for the second listening) listening approaches with the objective of minimizing the influence of task type on the reported strategies (Macaro et al., 2007). As some experts (such as White, Schramm, and Chamot, 2007) suggest, the students were allowed freedom of language choice, so they could decide whether they preferred to verbalize their thoughts either in English or in Spanish. In fact, the conversation started in Spanish and, once the students knew about their language freedom, they chose whether they preferred to continue in Spanish, change into English or combine both. The teacher adapted to the students' choice and replied accordingly.
- (4) Think-aloud training: In spite of Macaro et al.'s (2007) concern about the fact that the think-aloud training may be artificially channelling students' thought processes, we believe that, given the general unfamiliarity of the participants with such a protocol, training in how to think aloud is necessary as long as the training focuses exclusively on the procedure of the protocol. During this training, the interviewees listened to how a Hong Kong student of Spanish was actually thinking aloud while listening to an oral text in the target language.
- (5) First listening: The first listening was a one-way listening task in which students listened to a non-interactive text of 169 words and 1:32 minutes of duration. As we understand that the degree of difficulty of the task influences strategy use (Chamot and Kupper, 1989: 17), we selected a challenging but accessible text; in fact, the students were familiar with the topic (description of a city) and with the speaker's accent (peninsular Spanish). The teacher revealed the topic and the main features of the text and, once the students already knew this information, she asked

whether they were thinking of anything before listening. If they admitted so, the teacher encouraged them to elaborate on every single thought until the students expressed they were ready to listen. Only then, was the passage played. In this way, they listened to the passage for the first time and, at the pre-established natural discourse boundary, the text was paused and the students expressed the strategies they were using to understand it. There were two pauses during this first listening, one in the middle of the passage and one at the end. During both pauses, the teacher remained quiet in order to let the students think and speak freely and, when they required some help or stimulus, she posed some open-ended prompts. In our study, it was the teacher who decided when and how many times to stop the recording. This is because we agree with Cohen and Macaro (2010) that allowing the listeners to decide for themselves where to stop the recording (Laviosa, 2000; Murphy, 1985; Santos et al., 2008) may result in the listeners only stopping at problematic moments and therefore not reporting on unproblematic processing. We also believe that many participants would not ask to stop the recording at all, so verbalization would not take place.

- (6) Second listening: The second listening presented a similar structure to the first one except that, this time, the passage was played all at once with no intermediate pauses and, as a consequence, there was a slight move away from the actual processing of the task. The exchange between the interviewer and the interviewees followed exactly the same pattern, that is the teacher remained quiet in order not to alter thought processes.
- (7) Comprehension tasks: The second listening was followed by a comprehension task in which the students were asked to read and try to complete five comprehension questions. The reason why such tasks were presented after and not

before listening, as they normally were in class, is because, otherwise, students might focus on answering the questions instead of focusing on verbalizing the listening strategies they were using. Following Buck (2001), listening comprehension was operationally defined as the ability to process a relative extended sample of realistic spoken language in real time and to answer direct content or inference questions based on this language sample. In the first task, the students were asked to order the topics according to the order in which they were mentioned in the passage. In the second one, they should pick three tourist spots in the city out of six options. The third asked about the most famous attraction in the city, and the fourth focused on the reason for its popularity, both through multiple-choice questions. In the last one, the students had to decide whether the three given statements about several aspects of the city were true or false. Since such questions were presented in written Spanish, reading ability might constitute a confounding variable. However, we preferred to modify neither the language nor the format in which students used to access comprehension questions in class, because, otherwise, other confounding variables such as dealing with the unknown (they were not familiar with accessing questions in English) or memory (they needed to remember questions orally delivered) might arise. At this point, the teacher asked the students to read the questions carefully and express whether they thought they knew the answers or not. She also informed them that they would be able to listen one more time.

- (8) Third listening: The students listened for the third time with the objective of providing proper answers for the given questions.

- (9) Fourth listening with transcription: Finally, the students listened while they read the script of the passage in order to check their comprehension and identify any strategy that, otherwise, could have gone unnoticed.
- (10) Self-assessment: This final listening was followed by self-assessment questions in which the students were encouraged to reflect on: (a) the percentage of the text they understood (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, etc.); (b) whether they had any trouble understanding this specific oral passage, and, if so, which difficulties they faced; (c) the strategies they used to minimize such problems and their effectiveness, and (d) the aspects they would change in the future if they had to deal with a similar task.
- (11) Individual feedback from the teacher: The teacher provided the students with individual advice about the use of new strategies or the application of known ones according to their actual performance and disclosure during the interview. The students were also encouraged to ask questions about both listening comprehension and strategy use.
- (12) Evaluation: The teacher asked the students to assess the protocol by showing their degree of agreement (being 1: totally disagree; 2: slightly disagree; 3 slightly agree; 4: agree; 5: totally agree) with four given statements: the activity (or protocol) promotes reflection on my own learning process; the activity has helped me to understand what I do in order to comprehend oral Spanish; the activity has had a positive impact on my listening comprehension; I am willing to participate in a similar activity. Finally, the learner was asked to assess the entire activity in a general way by giving points from 0 to 10 (being the latter the best grade) and providing some optional comments.

- (13) Gratitude and farewell: The researcher thanked the students for their attendance, and said goodbye to them. This was the end of the 75-minute interview.

Analysis phase

The final phase consisted of the transcription and analysis of introspective data reflecting the strategies students employed while listening to a text in Spanish.

Regarding the transcription of think-aloud data, in the final protocol, we chose to provide a detailed transcription including documentation of features of oral speech, non-verbal communication, physical action, and teacher's interpretation of feelings (See Table 2).

Table 2 Sample of transcription (represents 0.8% of all the transcribed interviews)
First part of first listening WHILE LISTENING STUDENT 11: (Drawing) (Taking notes) STUDENT 10: (Taking notes) AFTER LISTENING ... ¹ BOTH STUDENTS: (Laughing) .. ² STUDENT 10: Hablando la general ideas about Salamanca y hablando... ³ la location. How to say "location"? TEACHER: ¿"Location"? La localización. STUDENT 10: Ah... la localización de Salamanca, eh .. de Madrid y y.. sobre la universidad, no sé (Laughing). Sí. Just some basical, basic information, I think. STUDENT 11: Does it mention something like the history? TEACHER: Why do you think that? STUDENT 11: Por qué .. credo que hablan sobre números. TEACHER: Has entendido números y, por eso, crees que hablan de historia. STUDENT 11: Ajam (Nodding). TEACHER: ¿Qué más habéis hecho para entender? STUDENT 10: Mmmmm, notas y .. ⁴ emmm presto atención a para entender... STUDENT 11: ... [Continues classmate's sentence] palabras... universidad ...

1. Key to transcription conventions: Long pause (more than three seconds)
2. Key to transcription conventions: Medium pause (between two and three seconds).
3. Key to transcription conventions: Termination of utterances.
4. Key to transcription conventions: Short pause (one second).

STUDENT 10: Y número, pero muy difícil, I think because not just similar to English, the way you express numbers, so I pay more attention to the numbers.

The analysis phase of the final think-aloud protocol involved listening to more than 679 minutes of recorded interviews, transcribing them during more than 2,800 minutes, reading and analysing the written text with the objective of finding common patterns, making categories according to those patterns which corresponded with listening strategies, and, finally, quantifying the number of strategies that were used.

4. Results and discussion

The process of transcription, linguistic analysis, categorization and calculation helped us to meet our first objective of identifying the listening strategies the participants used to complete the listening task at hand.

The categories identified after the analysis of the transcribed interviews corresponded with listening strategies and reflected all of the instances of strategy use found in the data. Table 3 shows the different types of listening strategies (31) and the total number of uses (398) employed by the Hong Kong students in order to understand the given oral text in Spanish. Of the 31 used strategies, ten are metacognitive, 16 are cognitive, and five are socio-affective.

Table 3	
Type and number of listening strategies reported by students	
LISTENING STRATEGY	USES (N)
Problem identification	51
Evaluation	38
Questioning for clarification	31
Improvement	27
Focusing attention	26
Decoded inferencing	24
Summarization	24
Repetition	20

Comprehension monitoring	19
Global prediction	16
Performance planning	14
Note taking	14
Grouping	13
Elaboration	12
Deduction	12
Inferencing	8
Translation	7
Prediction monitoring	6
Visual elaboration	6
Cooperation	5
Voice or intonation inferencing	5
Attention monitoring	3
Logic monitoring	3
Between parts inferencing	3
Asking for advice	3
Comprehension task checking	2
Transfer	2
Personal goal setting	1
Self-talk	1
Kinesic matching	1
Taking emotional temperature	1

It can be observed that the metacognitive strategies of problem identification and evaluation are the strategies that the participants used the most in this particular listening task. The extensive use of these metacognitive strategies appears to be task dependent, since both the objective of the think-aloud activity and the task situation contribute to the ability to evaluate and reflect about listening difficulties.

Despite the reason behind the use of these metacognitive strategies, we noted that only the most effective listeners (the ones in group 1 and 2) evaluated the effectiveness of their strategy use. On the contrary, none of the members in the third group, except for one, experienced such a reflection. These results are consistent with Vandergrift's (1997), since, in his study, only the more advanced learners reported to use the metacognitive strategies of evaluation. Based on our findings, which are supported by Vandergrift's

(1997), we can infer that the metacognitive strategies of evaluation may distinguish the successful from the less successful listeners.

In addition to problem identification and evaluation, focusing attention, questioning for clarification, improvement, decoded inferencing, summarization, repetition, comprehension monitoring, and global prediction are the ten most reported listening strategies by these Hong Kong students of Spanish. We can see that half of the ten more used strategies are metacognitive.

Unlike previous studies (such as Vandergrift, 2003) in which socio-affective strategies were barely verbalized, our students did report using them. In fact, the strategy of questioning for clarification is the third most employed with 31 uses. Nevertheless, it is important to notice how students informed to use just five socio-affective strategies, and two of them were only used by one student each. In this regard, we agree with Vandergrift (1997) that this might be due to the nature of the think-aloud procedure, since it is not conducive to eliciting the report of such a category of strategies. Furthermore, the context of the study together with the cultural values of the learner's society and the learner's goals might have an influence on choice and acceptability of listening strategies (Chamot, 2008), specially of the socio-affective ones.

Concerning such results, we must bear in mind that the chosen text might have influenced the types of strategies that the participants used. In this regard, as Graham et al. (2011) point out, the limited number of texts used for the verbal report may have limited the instances of strategy use elicited. We must also consider, as Vandergrift (2003) did, that, since the participants in this study were engaged in a one-way and non-participatory listening, the results of it will not necessarily apply to listening contexts that are more participatory and interactional in nature. Despite these limitations, we

understand that specific learners use specific listening strategies, and that some strategies are more appropriate and effective given the particular learning situation than others.

In order to address our second objective, we analysed the participants' open-ended reflections on the success of the strategies they employed, that is we analysed their replies to the question of the Self-assessment phase in which students were asked to report which listening strategies were the most effective ones during the given listening task. As there was no specification about the number of strategies they should provide, the number of reported strategies by the participants varies from 3 to none. In fact, as we mentioned before, only one of the members in group 3 evaluated the effectiveness of his/her strategy use; while all members in group 1 and 2 conducted such a self-evaluation.

In sum, 25 strategies were reported. The metacognitive strategy of focusing attention (five reports), the cognitive strategy of note taking (also five reports), and the socio-affective strategy of cooperation (three reports) were considered by the learners as the most effective strategies in this particular situation. The strategies of performance planning, comprehension monitoring, and global prediction were reported twice each; while the cognitive strategies of elaboration, visual elaboration, inferencing, summarization, translation, and grouping were reported once each. In this way, the students believed that these 12 different types of strategies were effective, and thus assisted their listening comprehension.

Given the students' self-assessment of the effectiveness of their strategy use, we decided to look closer at the individual use of the three strategies that were considered by the students as the most useful, namely the strategies of focusing attention, note taking, and cooperation. By having a glimpse of Table 4, we can see some differences in quantity of strategy use between the three groups of students. Table 4 shows how the uses of the strategies of note taking and focusing attention decreases from group 1 to group 3. In

group 1, all students employed the strategies of note taking and focusing attention. In group 2, five (out of seven) students used the strategy of note taking, and six of them employed the strategy of focusing attention. In group 3, however, only two of the six students employed the strategy of note taking, while only one of them used the strategy of planning attention. Concerning the use of the social strategy of cooperation, it was used by four learners in group 1, two members in group 2, and none in group 3.

Given the differences in quantity of use of the three strategies reported as the most effective ones between the most-, middle-, and less-effective listeners of this particular passage, we can deduce that the use of these three strategies may have a positive effect on listening comprehension, and thus may be distinguishing the more effective from the less effective listeners.

Table 4				
Students' number of uses of the three strategies reported as the most effective: note taking, focusing attention, and cooperation				
Group	Students	Note taking	Focusing attention	Cooperation
1	2	1	1	1
	8	1	2	1
	12	2	2	1
	13	1	3	
	15	1	1	
	19	1	1	1
2	1	1	3	
	3		3	
	7	1	2	
	9	1	2	
	10	1	3	1
	11	1		1
	14		2	
3	4			
	5	1		
	6			
	16			
	17	1		
	18		1	

Our third objective focuses on understanding the students' assessment of the protocol. The descriptive analysis of the participants' replies to the short evaluation questionnaire shows that the students agree that the developed and presented protocol, first, promotes reflection on their own learning process (mean: 4.11), second, helps them to understand what they do (both physically and mentally) in order to comprehend oral Spanish (mean: 4.00), and, third, has a positive impact on their listening comprehension (mean: 3.89). The learners also reported being willing to participate in a similar activity in the future (mean: 4.05). Concerning the general assessment of the entire protocol, the median of the points given by the participants is 7.95 (out of 10). Bearing in mind that the think-aloud protocol was voluntary and was not part of the course evaluation, the resulting median is extremely positive.

Additionally, the analysis of the voluntary comments provided by some of the students reveal that, according to the participants, the implemented think-aloud technique allows for one-on-one interaction, individual attention and immediate focus on problem-solving. Furthermore, they consider that the individual nature of the developed protocol promotes their interest, motivation and reflection.

5. Conclusions

The present article has presented the implemented think-aloud protocol. In respect with our first objective, we can conclude that the most reported strategies in this particular listening task are the metacognitive strategies of problem identification and evaluation. The analysis of the students' report of the effectiveness of the strategies they used shows that, according to the participants, the most effective strategies are the ones of focusing attention, note taking, and cooperation

In connection with our third objective, results point out that the participants assess this think-aloud activity positively, especially considering that this was a voluntary activity apart from their regular lessons and whose participation did not directly affect their final grade.

It is hoped that the research methodology and the outcomes presented here contribute to developments in the use of think-aloud protocols. According to White et al. (2007), such developments are some of the main methodological contributions from strategy research to the field of second language acquisition. It is also hoped that the think-aloud protocol we have presented promotes comparison across studies and expands the study of the methodological aspects of think-aloud protocols.

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